

Human information behaviour in contemporary spirituality

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STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

This presentation will highlight lesser-known realms of information science research by reporting on a recent study that analysed information behaviour in the domain of contemporary non-institutionalised spirituality.

Value of the contribution

Previously, scholars have studied the information practices of Christian church leaders, Catholic individuals, Muslim converts and Western Buddhists (e.g. Siracky, 2013; Michels, 2014; Gorichanaz, 2016; Guzik, 2017; Chabot, 2019). However, these works have concerned themselves with formalised religious traditions and do not represent the increasingly non-institutionalised manifestations of spirituality in contemporary Western society (van der Veer, 2009; Huss, 2014). Our presentation will bring attention to the steadily growing information research in the domain of contemplation and spirituality by exploring contemporary spiritual information interactions outside formalised religious settings.

Research Outline

Contemporary spirituality is often portrayed in popular culture as a profound pursuit of personal growth surrounded by searches for meaning, purpose, and value in life. These pursuits may be influenced by spiritual ideas and practices such as those in Hinduism, Buddhism, Taoism, Shamanism, Judaism, Christianity and Islam; however, what sets them apart is a fervent non-commitment to any formalised tradition. In sociology, scholars now suggest that these individual pursuits for meaning could be explained as a wider social anthropological phenomenon of *Seekership* or spiritual seeking (Sutcliffe, 2016).

In addition to engagements with documentary information sources, spiritual seeking can involve various contemplative practices such as meditation, chanting, retreat, pilgrimage, labyrinth walking, journaling and dialogue. Many of these practices have their origins in spiritual traditions and may help facilitate informative and transformative outcomes (Latham, Hartel, Gorichanaz, 2020). However, the precise relationship between spiritual information seeking and contemplative spiritual practice is not well understood. To this end, our study investigated

contemporary spiritual seeking and its informational features for the information science research community.

We conducted semi-structured interviews with thirteen spiritual teachers and speakers electronically through Zoom's online video conferencing platform. Our interview strategy aimed to gather generalisations from each participant in order to attain a detailed description of contemporary spiritual seeking. Most interviews were about 45 minutes long. All participants spoke English and had spent a considerable number of years speaking to Western audiences in contemporary spirituality. In addition, participants had a history of engaging with spiritual information and could articulate aspects of contemporary spirituality without associating with traditional religiosity. However, since our interviewees were purposively selected to represent non-institutionalised Western spirituality, our findings cannot comprehensively represent all spiritual pursuits in contemporary society.

In analysing each interview transcript, we looked for answers to the following questions: (1) What is spiritual seeking? (2) What questions do spiritual seekers have? and (3) What does spiritual seeking look like informationally?

Our participants characterised spiritual seeking as a search for something deeper, a search for something higher, and a search inward. They described spiritual seeking as a persistent long-term endeavour to find an answer to one's problems and explained that contemporary spiritual seekers sought spiritual information as a result of affective, developmental and metaphysical concerns. Moreover, our analysis indicated that spiritual information seeking behaviour incorporated practices such as prayer, yoga and meditation, and contemporary spiritual information interactions were facilitated through spiritual retreats, meditation classes, yoga classes and online social platforms. Therefore, contemporary spiritual seeking could amalgamate conventional epistemological inquiry with contemplative and embodied forms of information behaviour.

In conclusion, our presentation will demonstrate a contextual approach to understanding human information behaviour in underexplored domains such as contemplation and spirituality.

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